

PHRASEOLOGY AS A BRANCH OF LEXICOLOGY

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Abstract: The article is to analyze the ways of translation of stylistically marked phraseological units which are considered to be one of the main aspects of English

Keywords: Phraseology, combination, terminological, phraseologisms, linguistic, morphology, word-combinations, Paradoxically, idioms generally imply, Polysemantic.

ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЯ КАК РАЗДЕЛ ЛЕКСИКОЛОГИИ

Аннотация: Статья посвящена анализу способов перевода стилистически маркированных фразеологизмов, которые считаются одним из основных аспектов английского языка.

Ключевые слова: фразеология, сочетание, терминология, фразеологизмы, лингвистика, морфология, словосочетания, парадоксально, фразеологизмы, общеимплицитные, многозначные.

INTRODUCTION

Phraseology is a science about phraseological units; i.e. stable combination of words. Phraseology is a treasure of a language which reflects the history, the cultures, and way of life of any nation. Phraseology often express national character. The fund of English Phraseology is rich in national, international, borrowed, of terminological and non – terminological phraseological units. Human factor takes the basic place in phrase formation as the majority of phraseologisms are connected with different spheres of human activity. The factor of address is the most important element of communication. Besides that human tries to describe out world objects by human features .Ch. Bally confirmed:

MATERIALS AND METHODS

“A person always describes the features and trying of his own personality by all object out of world”. V.G. Gak gave his opinion about Ch. Bally’s words as "Therefore human is in the centre of attention himself he tries to describe out world by own usage.

Language phraeologisms considered to be the general law of the development of nominating means in the language”. By this we understand that human state, human feelings are describe by different objects of inanimate world, space, animal world, and myth means.

Phraseologisms are highly informative units of a language. They can be considered as the “decoration”. Though there have been a number of researches on phraseology, it is one of language universals, that there is no language without phraseologisms. So, every work on phraseological units is considered to be fresh which appear new and brand features every time. English phraseology is rich and is has deep history"

Paradoxically as its seem the first dictionary in which theoretical principles for the selection of English phraseological units were elaborated was published in our country. The term itself phraseological units denote a specific group of phrases was introduced by Russian linguists and is generally accepted in our country.

Attempts have been made to approach the problem of phraseology indifferent ways. Up till now, however, there is an essential feature of phraseological units as distinguished

from other word groups and the nature of phrases that can be properly termed phraseological units.

The complexity of the problem may be largely accounted for by the fact that the borderline between free of variable word - groups and phraseological units is not clearly defined. The so called free word - groups are only relatively free as collectability of their member words is fundamentally delimited by their lexical and grammatical variability which makes at least some of them very close to set phrases.

Phraseological units are comparatively stable and semantically unchangeable. Between the extremes of complete motivation and variability of member words on the one hand and lack of motivation combined with complete stability of the lexical components and grammatical structure on the other hands. There are numerous borderline cases.

However the existing terms, e.g. set phrases, idioms, word - equivalents, reflect to a certain extent the main debatable issues of phraseology which centre on

The divergent views concerning the nature and essential features of phraseological units as distinguished from the so called free word groups. The term set - phrase implies that the basic criterion of differentiation is stability of the lexical component grammatical structure of word - group. The term idiom generally implies that the essential feature of the linguistic units under consideration is idiomatic or lack of motivation.

This term habitually used by English and American linguistics is very often treated synonymous with the term "phraseological unit" universally accepted in our country. The term "word equivalent" stresses not only the semantic but also the function is speech as single words.

These differences in terminology reflect certain differences in the main criteria used to distinguish between word - groups and specific type of linguistic units generally known as phraseology. These criteria and the ensuring classification are done below.

Phraseological units are habitually defined as non - motivated word groups that can be freely made up in speech but are reproduced as ready made units. This definition proceeds from the assumption that the essential features of phraseological units are stability of the lexical components and lack of motivation.

It is consequently assumed that unlike components of free word groups which may vary according to the needs of communication, member words of phraseological units are always reproduced as single unchangeable collocations.

Languages differ greatly in their idiosyncrasies i.e. in the forms which they have adopted, in the peculiarities of their usage and the combinative power of words, in idiomatic forms of expression.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is to be marked in this connection that of all the ambiguous terms employed in linguistics, none seems to call for more careful definition than the term "idiom". An idiom or idiomatic phrase is often defined as phrase, developing a meaning which can't be readily analyzed into the several distinct ideas which would ordinarily be expressed by the words composing the phrase. It transcends the ordinary syntactical constructions and must be studied as a grammatical unit, or entity in itself.

On the other hand, "idiom" is a very broad term and includes all the peculiarities and idiosyncrasies of the language constructions, and other conventional practices of an unusual character. Phraseology is also a term of wide inclusions but seems preferable for describing

various, kind of phrases characterized by different degrees of stability and idiomatic in a given language.

CONCLUSIONS

A major stimulus to intensive studies of phraseology in Russian linguistics was V.V. Vinogradov's research carried out in the history of the Russian vocabulary. The classification suggested by V. V. Vinogradov has been widely adopted by linguistic working on other languages.

Investigation of English phraseology as initiated by A.V. Koonin, whose dictionary of English phraseologisms has much valuable information on the theory of phraseology.

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